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DEVELOPMENT OF THE BUSINESS ECOSYSTEM IN AGRICULTURAL BUSINESS IN THE CONDITIONS OF EUROPEAN INTEGRATION AND WARTIME

The main tasks of creating a favorable business environment for the development of agrarian entrepreneurship in the context of European integration are rebranding (attraction of investment resources); creating a positive image for investors; simplification of administrative procedures. Different directions of functioning of entrepreneurship ecosystems in agrarian business should be aimed at the development of entrepreneurship, strengthening its stability and increasing activity, strengthening the socio-economic economy of agrarian production, improving the welfare of citizens in the countryside. The world economy has an example of successful entrepreneurship ecosystems, in particular: the Berlin ecosystem (Germany, segment of the creative economy), the Stockholm technological ecosystem (Sweden, the industry and innovation sector), the Shenzhen city ecosystem (China, the high-tech sector), the Tel Aviv ecosystem (Israel, sphere of high technologies and startups), Silicon Valley (USA, sphere of high technologies and innovations), Bangalore ecosystem (India, IT sphere), London financial ecosystem (Great Britain, sphere of financial technologies and innovations in the fintech sector).

Ecosystems of entrepreneurship in agrarian business are successfully implemented in Brazil, the USA and other countries of the world. In particular, the Danish ecosystem is focused on the rational use of limited state resources and the development of environmentally friendly technologies in agriculture through the cooperation of entrepreneurs with research organizations with the assistance of the government. also, Israel's ecosystem promotes the integration of business entities in agriculture and allows the introduction of technologies for the effective use of water, the use of drones for the purpose of monitoring crops and the implementation of technological processes. In the Netherlands, an agricultural ecosystem has been formed with the participation of farmers, startups and government bodies, which jointly ensure the introduction of innovations and the development of high technologies in agriculture, the development of greenhouses, irrigation

systems and modern methods of cultivating agricultural plants and raising animals.

The ecosystem of entrepreneurship in agrarian business has transformed into a powerful model of interaction between business entities, consumers of agricultural products, and support and service organizations for business entities. Various forms of interaction of business entities developed on the basis of various types of integration, cooperation, etc. Common options for economic cooperation are integration associations, hubs, business incubators and accelerators, agricultural cooperatives, production and innovation clusters, etc. Agrarian clusters and ecosystems of entrepreneurship in agrarian business are distinguished by similarity. They reflect the interaction of various business entities and positively influence the state of business. In Ukraine, we have only the initial stage of introducing the ecosystem approach in the development of entrepreneurship in agriculture. Most entrepreneurial ecosystems in agrarian business are based on the cooperation of large entrepreneurs (for example, agricultural holdings) with other players in the market environment [1, p. 58-60]. For example, the AgroGeneration ecosystem is focused on implementing GPS systems, telemetry; on the use of specialized equipment to increase productivity, etc. The Epicenter-K ecosystem promotes the development of its own agricultural production. The ecosystem with the participation of Myronivsk bread products promotes the introduction of new production technologies, digital management and monitoring systems. The Agroprosperis ecosystem makes it possible to implement new technologies for optimizing management and production processes.

The current trends in the development of agrarian entrepreneurship ecosystems in the conditions of European integration and wartime are the following: the introduction of Digital Agriculture, which is focused on making informed management decisions based on the use of IT, artificial intelligence, data analytics, drones, optimization of production processes [2, p. 18-20]; activation of medium, small, micro-businesses in the countryside through the development of cooperative and integration relations, introduction of resource rationalization technologies, improvement of business performance, increase of competitive and adaptive survival potential [3, p. 453-455]; the production of organic products and the implementation of eco-agriculture aimed at supporting biological diversity, the spread of organic methods of growing plants and animals; optimization of supply chains (logistics from the manufacturer to the final consumer; increased transparency in product management); formation of tourist infrastructure in the village; Green Energy Agriculture (increase in generation from renewable sources); development of Agriculture Finance through payment systems and

financial instruments. The ecosystem includes up-to-date digital solutions that determine the health status of fruit and field crops based on photographs, which can be scaled up for other types of trees and plants. Obtaining relevant and objective information about the state of plants using Internet services will improve the exchange of information between specialists and expert consultants.

Thus, in the process of research, it was established that the development of entrepreneurship ecosystems in agriculture is a promising mechanism for the European integration of economic entities. Ecosystems reflect a more optimal cooperation between business entities and their partners-players in business. The spread of ecosystems in entrepreneurship in agriculture will allow to activate the initiative of small and micro-businesses in the countryside, will contribute to the introduction of digital technologies, the optimization of the supply chains of agricultural raw materials and food products, the development of eco-agriculture, the strengthening of the financial management system, green energy, green and rural tourism, etc. The development of the ecosystem of entrepreneurship in agrarian business can have a synergistic effect, provided that the subjects of entrepreneurship in agriculture are fully rebuilt in the post-war period. Today, the ecosystem of entrepreneurship in agrarian business is functioning, but the strategy of their functioning very often cannot withstand turbulent flows.

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